

Implementation of Combinatorial Algorithms using Optimization Techniques

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ABSTRACT

In theoretical computer science, combinatorial optimization problems are about finding an optimal item from a finite set of objects. Combinatorial optimization is the process of searching for maxima or minima of an unbiased function whose domain is a discrete and large configuration space. It often involves determining the way to efficiently allocate resources used to find solutions to mathematical problems. Applications for combinatorial optimization include determining the optimal way to deliver packages in logistics applications, determining taxi best route to reach a destination address, and determining the best allocation of jobs to people. Some common problems involving combinatorial optimizations are the Knapsack problem, the Job Assignment problem, and the Travelling Salesman problem. This paper proposes three new optimized algorithms for solving three combinatorial optimization problems namely the Knapsack problem, the Job Assignment problem, and the Traveling Salesman respectively. The Knapsack problem is about finding the most valuable subset of items that fit into the knapsack. The Job Assignment problem is about assigning a person to a job with the lowest total cost possible. The Traveling Salesman problem is about finding the shortest tour to a destination city through travelling a given set of cities. Each problem is to be tackled separately. First, the design is proposed, then the pseudo code is created along with analyzing its time complexity. Finally, the algorithm is implemented using a high-level programming language. As future work, the proposed algorithms are to be parallelized so that they can execute on multiprocessing environments making their execution time faster and more scalable.

KEYWORDS: Combinatorial Algorithms, Optimization Techniques, Knapsack, Job Assignment, Traveling Salesman

I. KNAPSACK PROBLEM

The knapsack problem is a problem in combinatorial optimization [1]. Given n items of weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n and values v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n and a knapsack (container) of capacity W . The problem is to find the most valuable subset of items that fit into the knapsack [2].

A. Proposed Solution

The algorithms is based on exhaustive search approach which suggests generating every combinational object of the problem and performing the appropriate calculations. The algorithm use three one-dimensional arrays, one to store the item weights, another one to store the item values, and a last one to store the generated subsets.

B. Design

Figure 1 shows the process flow diagram of the Knapsack problem design

Figure 1: Process Flow for the Knapsack problem

C. Algorithm

```

//ALGORITHM Knapsack (itemsValue[n], items
Weight[n])
// Knapsack Problem
// INPUT: itemsValue[n] , itemsWeight[n]
// OUTPUT: optimalSubset: array of integers
ITEMS_COUNT: integer constant that holds the # of
items
itemsValue[n]: array of integers that holds item
Values
itemsWeight[n]: array of integers that holds item
Weights
    
```

bitString[ITEMS_COUNT]: array of flags that holds a particular subset
 optimalSubset[ITEMS_COUNT]: array of flags that holds the subset of items with highest total value
 knapsackCapacity : integer that holds the Capacity of the Knapsack
 optimalValue: integer that holds the highest Value calculated after each subset
 sumValues: integer that holds the sum of all items values for a given subset
 sumWeights: integer that holds the sum of all items weights for a given subset

BEGIN

```

optimalValue ← 0
// Step1: Generates integer numbers
FOR i ← 0 TO Pow(2,ITEMS_COUNT) DO
{
// Step2: Convert integer Numbers to binary numbers
// Step3: Generating Subsets
j ← 0
WHILE i <> 0
{
bitString[j] ← i MOD 2
i ← i/2
}
// Step4: Calculate the Item values corresponding to each subset
sumValues<-0
sumWeights<-0
FOR k ← 0 TO ITEMS_COUNT DO
{
// Replaces TRUE flag with its corresponding Item value
IF bitString[k] = TRUE THEN
{
sumValues <- sumValues + itemsValue[k]
sumWeights <- sumWeights + itemsWeight[k]
}
}
k ← k+1
}
// Step5: Store the highest value with its corresponding subset
IF (sumWeights <= knapsackCapacity AND sumValues > optimalValue)
THEN
{
optimalValue <- sumValues
FOR p←0 TO ITEMS_COUNT DO
{
optimalSubset[p] <- bitString[p]
p <- p+1
}
}
i ← i+1
} // end of step1 FOR LOOP
// Step6: Return the Subset that has highest Items value
RETURN optimalSubset
END
    
```

D. Analysis

The proposed algorithm can find the optimal subset of items with their corresponding optimal value while falling under the below efficiency class:
Knapsack (a[n],b[n]) ∈ O n² (n² > n)
Knapsack (a[n],b[n]) ∈ Ω 1 (1 < n)
Knapsack (a[n],b[n]) ∈ Φ n (n = n)

Performance wise, it requires about 9 milliseconds to handle the problem with 50 items.

E. Implementation

Figure 2 depicts the screenshot of the program that implements the Knapsack problem using C#.NET [3].

Figure 2: The Knapsack Program

II. JOB ASSIGNMENT PROBLEM

The assignment problem is a fundamental combinatorial optimization problem [4]. Given n people who need to be assigned to n jobs, one person per job. The cost of *i*th person is assigned to *j*th job is stored in *table[i][j]*. The problem is to find an assignment with the lowest total cost [5].

A. Proposed Solution

Developing an algorithms based on the brute force technique which tests and evaluates all possible objects combinations involved in the problem and performs appropriate calculations. The algorithm uses a one-dimentional array to store permutations and a two-dimentional array to store Person/Job cost

B. Design

Figure 3 shows the process flow diagram of the Job Assignment problem design

Figure 3: Process Flow for the Job Assignment problem

C. Algorithm

```

// ALGORITHM Assignment (table[n][n] , COUNTER)
// Person/Job Assignment Problem
// INPUT: table[n][n] , COUNTER
    
```

```

// OUTPUT: optimalList : array of integers
table[n][n]: 2D integer array that Stores all costs
entered by the user
COUNTER: integer that holds the # of persons(or the
# of jobs)
list[COUNTER]: array of integers that holds
permutation
pointers[COUNTER]: array of integers that holds
present direction of each permutation
increasingPtr[COUNTER]: array of integers that holds
left to right arrows -> -> -> ....
decreasingPtr[COUNTER]: array of integers that holds
right to left arrows <- <- <- ....
optimalSum: integer that holds the lower cost per
person/job assignment
optimalList [COUNTER]: array of integers that holds
the permutation with the lower cost
mobile: integer that holds the mobile element
mobileIndex: integer that holds the index of the
mobile element
flag: boolean variable that indicates if a mobile exists
or not
temp: integer used FOR swapping purposes
sum: integer that holds the cost of a particular
permutation instance

BEGIN
optimalSum ← INFINITY
//Fill array lists with 1 2 3 4 5 6...(depending on
variable COUNTER)
FOR i←0 TO COUNTER DO
{
list[i] ← i+1
i ← i+1
}
//Initialize pointers <- <- <- ....
FOR i ← COUNTER-1 TO 0 DO
{
pointers[i] ← i-1
i ← i+1
}
//Initialize increasingPtr -> -> -> ....
FOR i←0 TO COUNTER DO
{
increasingPtr[i] ← i+1
i ← i+1
}
//Initialize decreasingPtr <- <- <- ....
FOR i←COUNTER-1 TO 0 DO
{
decreasingPtr[i] ← i-1
i ← i+1
}
// Johnson-Trotter ALGORITHM
// Generates Permutations
FOR i←0 TO fac(COUNTER)-1 DO
{
//Calculate the cost for each permutation
instance
sum ← 0
FOR j←0 TO COUNTER DO
{
sum ← sum+table[j,list[j]-1]
j ← j+1
}
// Holds the lowest sum
IF sum < optimalSum THEN
{
optimalSum ← sum
FOR k←0 TO COUNTER DO
{
optimalList[k]←list[k]
k ← k+1
}
}
mobile ← 0
mobileIndex ← 0
flag ← false
//Step1 : Find the largest Mobile
FOR i←0 TO COUNTER DO
{
IF(pointers[i]<>1 && pointers[i]<>COUNTER
AND list[i]>mobile AND
list[pointers[i]]<list[i])
THEN
{
mobile ← list[i]
mobileIndex ← i
flag ← TRUE
}
i ← i+1
}
// Step2: test whether a mobile was found
// Step3: Swap the mobile with the element that it
points to
// Step4: Swap the pointers of mobile and the
element that it points to
// Step5: Reverse Directions of all elements that
are greater than mob
IF flag=TRUE THEN
{
// Swap the mobile with the element that it
points to
list[mobileIndex] ← list[pointers[mobileIndex]]
list[pointers[mobileIndex]] ← mobile
IF(pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]=mobileIndex) THEN
{
// Indicates the mobile is at the left side
IF(pointers[mobileIndex] > mobileIndex)
THEN
{
// Swap the pointers of mobile and the
element that it points to
Temp←pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]
pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]←pointers
[mobileIndex]+1
pointers[mobileIndex]←temp-1
}
ELSE // Indicates the mobile is at the right
side
{
// Swap the pointers of mobile and the
element that it points to
}
}
}
}

```

```

Temp ← pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]
pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]] ← pointer
s[mobileIndex]-1
pointers[mobileIndex] ← temp+1
}
}
}
// Reverse Directions
FOR i ← 0 TO COUNTER DO
{
IF list[i] > mobile THEN
IF pointers[i] ← increasingPtr[i] THEN
pointers[i] ← decreasingPtr[i]
ELSE IF pointers[i] ← decreasingPtr[i] THEN
pointers[i] ← increasingPtr[i]
i ← i+1
}
}
//Calculate the cost FOR the last permutation
instance
sum ← 0
FOR j ← 0 TO COUNTER DO
{
sum ← sum+table[j,list[j]-1]
j ← j+1
}
// Holds the lowest sum
IF sum < optimalSum THEN
{
optimalSum ← sum
FOR k ← 0 TO COUNTER DO
{
optimalList[k] ← list[k]
k ← k+1
}
}
// optimal list should hold the less costly
person/job assignment
RETURN optimalList

```

END

D. Analysis

The proposed algorithm can find the optimal person/job assignment with its corresponding lowest cost. It is very practical even on large number of persons, however it exhausts processing time due to Johnson-trotter algorithm [6] whose order of growth is always exponential. The algorithm falls under the below efficiency class:

- Assignment (table[n][n], c) ∈ O n³ (n³ > n²)
- Assignment (table[n][n], c) ∈ Ω n (n < n²)
- Assignment (table[n][n], c) ∈ Φ n² (n² = n²)

Performance wise, it requires 12 seconds to handle a problem with 100 jobs 100! = 9.33262154439441 52681699238856267e+157 permutations

E. Implementation

Figure 4 depicts the screenshot of the program that implements the Job Assignment problem using C#.NET.

Figure 4: The Job Assignment Program

III. TRAVELING SALESMAN PROBLEM

The Traveling Salesman Problem is a classic algorithmic problem in the field of computer science that focuses on optimization [7]. The problem ask to find the shortest tour through a given set of n cities or nodes that visits each city exactly once before returning to the city where it started [8].

A. Proposed Solution

Exhaustive search technique is so far the most appropriate approach to solve this problem. It consists of generating all possible paths with their corresponding lengths so eventually the shortest path can be identified. The algorithm uses a one-dimensional array to store permutations, a one-dimensional array to store distinct cities, and a two-dimensional array to store from city, to city, and length variables.

B. Design

Figure 5 shows the process flow diagram for the Traveling Salesman problem design

Figure 5: Process Flow for the Traveling Salesman problem

C. Algorithm

```

// ALGORITHM Salesman(table[n][3], startCity)
// Person/Job Assignment Problem
// INPUT: table[n][n], startCity
// OUTPUT: optimalList : array of characters

```

- cities[citiesCounter]: array of characters holds Distinct cities
- newList[citiesCounter+1]: array of characters that holds: startcity+permutation+startcity
- citiesCounter: integer holds # of distinct cities
- startCity: Character holds the name of the start city
- table[n][3]: 2D integer array that Stores all routes with their corresponding length
- list[citiesCounter-1]: array of characters that holds permutation
- pointers[citiesCounter-1]: array of integers that holds present direction of each permutation

increasingPtr[citiesCounter-1]: array of integers that holds left to right arrows -> -> ->
decreasingPtr[citiesCounter-1]: array of integers that holds right to left arrows <- <- <-
optimalSum: integer that holds the shortest path summation
optimalList[citiesCounter+1]: array of characters that holds the permutation with the shortest path
mobile: integer that holds the mobile element
mobileIndex: integer that holds the index of the mobile element
flag: boolean variable that indicates if a mobile exists or not
temp: integer used for swapping purposes
sum: integer that holds the cost of a particular permutation instance

BEGIN

//Step1: Recognize and store in array cities only the distinct cities
i ← 0

WHILE(*i* < *citiesCounter*) DO

```
{
  IF table[i][1] <> cities[i] THEN
    i ← i+1
  ELSE
    {
      i ← citiesCounter+1
      s ← i
    }
}
```

// Adding the found city to the array

IF *i* = *citiesCounter* THEN

```
{
  cities[citiesCounter] ← table[s][1]
  citiesCounter ← citiesCounter+1
}
```

//Step2: create an array named list that contains all distinct cities

k ← 0

FOR *i* ← 0 TO *citiesCounter* DO

```
{
  IF cities[i] <> startCity THEN
    {
      list[k] ← cities[i]
      k ← k+1
    }
}
```

i ← *i*+1

}

//Initialize pointers <- <- <-

FOR *i* ← *citiesCounter*-1 TO 0 DO

```
{
  pointers[i] ← i-1
  i ← i+1
}
```

//Initialize increasingPtr -> -> ->

FOR *i* ← 0 TO *citiesCounter* DO

```
{
  increasingPtr[i] ← i+1
  i ← i+1
}
```

//Initialize decreasingPtr <- <- <-

FOR *i* ← *citiesCounter*-1 TO 0 DO

```
{
  decreasingPtr[i] ← i-1
  i ← i+1
}
```

FOR *i* ← 0 TO *fac*(*citiesCounter*)-1 DO

```
{
  // Step3 : Add the startcity at the beginning & at the end
  newList[0] ← startCity

  k ← 1
  FOR s ← 0 TO citiesCounter DO
    {
      newList[k] ← list[s]
      k ← k+1
      s ← s+1
    }
}
```

newList[*citiesCounter*] ← startCity

//Step4: Calculate Length

Sum ← 0

i ← 0

j ← 0

WHILE *i* < *citiesCounter*-1 AND *j* < *n*-1 DO

```
{
  IF (newList[i] = table[j,0] AND
  newList[i+1] = table[j,1])
  THEN
    {
      Sum ← sum+table[j,2]
      i ← i+1
      j ← 0
    }
  ELSE j ← j+1
}
```

// store the shortest path

IF *sum* < *optimalSum* THEN

```
{
  optimalSum ← sum
  FOR s ← 0 TO s < citiesCounter DO
    {
      optimalList[s] ← newList[s]
      s ← s+1
    }
}
```

// Johnson-Trotter ALGORITHM

// Step5: Generates Permutations

mobile ← '' // small value

mobileIndex ← 0

flag ← FALSE

// Step1 : Find the largest Mobile

FOR *i* ← 0 TO *citiesCounter* DO

```
{
  IF (pointers[i] <> 1 AND
  pointers[i] <> citiesCounter-1
  AND list[i] > mobile AND
  list[pointers[i]] < list[i])
  THEN
    {
      mobile ← list[i]
      mobileIndex ← i
    }
}
```

```

    flag ← true
  }
  i ← i+1
}
//Step2: test whether a mobile was found
//Step3: Swap the mobile with the element that
it points to
//Step4: Swap the pointers of mobile and the
element that it points to
//Step5: Reverse Directions of all elements that
are greater than mobile
IF flag=TRUE THEN
{
  // Swap the mobile with the element that it
  points to

  list[mobileIndex] ←
  list[pointers[mobileIndex]]
  list[pointers[mobileIndex]] ← mobile

  IF(pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]=mobileIn
  dex) THEN
  {
    // Indicates the mobile is at the left side
    IF(pointers[mobileIndex] > mobileIndex)
    THEN
    {
      // Swap the pointers of mobile and the
      element that it points to
      Temp←pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]
      pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]←pointer
      s[mobileIndex]+1
      pointers[mobileIndex]←temp-1
    }
    ELSE // Indicates the mobile is at the right
    side
    {
      // Swap the pointers of mobile and the
      element that it points to
      Temp←pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]
      pointers[pointers[mobileIndex]]←pointer
      s[mobileIndex]-1
      pointers[mobileIndex]←temp+1
    }
  }
}
// Reverse Directions
FOR i←0 TO citiesCounter DO
{
  IF list[i]>mobile THEN
    IF pointers[i]←increasingPtr[i] THEN
      pointers[i]←decreasingPtr[i]
    ELSE IF pointers[i]←decreasingPtr[i] THEN
      pointers[i]←increasingPtr[i]

  i ← i+1
}
}
RETURN optimalList

```

END

D. Analysis

The proposed algorithm can find the shortest path among many alternatives starting from a given city, passing through all the available cities only once to end at the same starting point. Even though it is based on Johnson-Trotter algorithm to generate permutations, the proposed algorithm is considered quite efficient due to the complexity of the original problem. Therefore to solve a complex problem such the traveling salesman problem, somehow you are going to lose some processing time. The algorithm falls under the below efficiency class:

Salesman (table[n][3] , sCity) € O n³ (n³ > n²)
 Salesman (table[n][3] , sCity) € Ω n (n < n²)
 Salesman (table[n][3] , sCity) € Φ n² (n² = n²)

Performance wise, it requires 17 seconds for a problem with 100 cities
 (100! = 9.3326215443944152681699238856267e+157 permutations)

E. Implementation

Figure 6 depicts the screenshot of the program that implements the Traveling Salesman problem using C#.NET.

Figure 6: The Traveling Salesman Program

IV. Conclusions & Future Work

This paper proposed three new optimized algorithms for solving three combinatorial optimization problems namely the Knapsack problem, the Job Assignment problem, and the Traveling Salesman problem respectively. Each problem was tackled from a design, analysis, and implementation point of views. The proposed designs showed the optimized versions of the algorithms while listing their complete pseudo code. Furthermore, a thorough time complexity analysis was performed to finally end up implementing the algorithms and testing them using C#.NET.

As future work, the proposed algorithms are to be parallelized using multithreading and multiprogramming techniques so as to speeding up their execution time and making them more adaptable to large computing architectures.

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References

- [1] Caccetta, L., Kulanoot, A, "Computational Aspects of Hard Knapsack Problems". Nonlinear Analysis, 47 (8): 5547–5558, 2001
- [2] Poirriez, Vincent; Yanev, Nicola; Andonov, Rumen, "A hybrid algorithm for the unbounded knapsack problem", Discrete Optimization, 6 (1): 110–124, 2009
- [3] Petzold, Charles, "Programming Microsoft Windows with C#", Microsoft Press. ISBN 0-7356-1370-2, 2002
- [4] Munkres, James, "Algorithms for the Assignment and Transportation Problems", Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 5 (1): 32–38, 1957
- [5] Brualdi, Richard A., "Combinatorial matrix classes. Encyclopedia of Mathematics and Its Applications", Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, ISBN 978-0-521-86565-4, 2006
- [6] Dershowitz, Nachum, "A simplified loop-free algorithm for generating permutations", Nordisk Tidskr Informations, 15 (2): 158–164, 1957
- [7] Cook, William, "In Pursuit of the Traveling Salesman: Mathematics at the Limits of Computation", Princeton University Press, ISBN 9780691152707, 2012
- [8] Steinerberger, Stefan, "New Bounds for the Traveling Salesman Constant", Advances in Applied Probability, (47): 27–36, 2015.

